

ENTERPRETATIVE DECONSTRUCTION STRATEGIES

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ANNOTATION

The architectonics of Derrida's work implies that it is devoid of the idea of linearity and continuity of writing. He says about his works "Writing and Difference" and "Of Grammatology": "These things cannot be imagined as easily as you might think. In any case, the two 'volumes' falling in the middle of each other, as you can see, resemble a strange geometry that appears contemporary with these texts..."

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1.5. Interpretative strategies

J.Culler in his work "On Deconstruction": Theory and Criticism of Poststructuralism" expresses the general purpose of all hermeneutic strategies of deconstruction as follows: "To deconstruct a discourse is to show how it undermines the philosophy it asserts, or the hierarchical oppositions on which it relies, by identifying in the text the rhetorical operations that produce the supposed ground of argument, the key concept or premise."

Deconstruction does not aim to prove, reject, or confirm the truth. On the contrary, all these concepts in deconstruction lie under the sign of erasure as one of the names of the metaphysics of logocentrism.

Within the framework of deconstructionist hermeneutics, the following interpretative strategies can be distinguished:

1. The strategy of eliminating binary oppositions - simultaneously eliminating the tradition of logocentrism;
2. Terminological strategy - deconstructing the terminological apparatus of metaphysics;
3. The strategy of approaching meaning as a capability;
4. Marginalization strategy;
5. Strategy of graphematic embeddings.

We will consider these strategies sequentially.

7.5.7. Strategy for eliminating binary oppositions

Derrida views the structure of philosophical theory as a game of relationships, oppositions, and differentiations (differences). Therefore, when interpreting the theory, it is crucial to first consider the oppositions operating within it. Accordingly, this strategy involves the explication of binary oppositions that are traditional in Western metaphysical traditions, such as: speech / writing, male / female, truth / falsehood, literal meaning / metaphorical, meaningful / symbolic, and their deconstruction.

In such oppositions in metaphysics, the first (left) term holds a superior status over the second (right) term, and it is viewed as "the complexity, negation, manifestation, or downfall of the first." For Derrida, such hierarchical oppositions constitute the essence of the logocentrism he criticizes. Deconstruction aims to dismantle these oppositions by equalizing their status and viewing them as effects of fundamental differentiation. As J.R. Searle notes in his article "Reversed Word," deconstruction primarily attempts to demonstrate that the second (right) term is actually fundamental, while the left is a particular case of the right; the right term is considered the condition of possibility for the left. Derrida also emphasizes the importance of this approach: "Deconstructing an opposition means, first and foremost, overturning the hierarchy at a given moment." Ignoring this stage of reversal would mean overlooking the contradictory and subordinate structure of the opposition. He clarifies that this is not about a chronological stage, stating, "The necessity of this phase is systematic, hence it is a constant necessity of analysis, as the hierarchy of binary opposition always reconstitutes itself."

But this is only the first stage. The goal is not to replace the opposition. The main objective is to completely eliminate any centralization and destroy the oppositions. For this, it is shown that the existing metaphysical oppositions are based on a general, but not metaphysical, concept that has been deconstructed: for example, archi-writing.

J. Culler schematically shows the elements of this strategic process :

(A) demonstrates that the opposition is expressed through metaphysical and ideological falsehoods, where:

(1) defining its foundations and role in the system of metaphysical meanings is a task that may require a broad analysis of a certain number of texts

(2) showing how it breaks down in texts that form it and rely on it;

(B) at the same time, the opposition is supported by:

(1) Its use in argumentation (speech and writing or literature and philosophy are not errors that should be rejected, but the main source of evidence) and

(2) its restoration through complete transformation, which gives it a different status and impulse.

The elimination of the binary opposition "external / internal" leads to the violation of the opposition "text / commentary," "text / interpretation," and they are considered as follows.

1.5.2. Terminological Strategy

Within the framework of the terminological strategy, in turn, several strategies can be distinguished:

- deconstructive analysis of metaphysical concepts;
- linguistic-comparative analysis of terms;
- analysis independent of specific terms of one philosopher or another;
- Negative distinction strategy;
- an antimetaphysical strategy for self-erasure (crossing out) of the term;
- a strategy for defining key concepts.

Let's examine each of these sub-strategies one by one.

Deconstructive analysis of metaphysical concepts

In his programmatic work "Letter to a Japanese Friend," Derrida emphasizes: "...the question of deconstruction is also, from beginning to end, the question of translation and of the language of concepts, of the conceptual corpus of so-called 'Western' metaphysics." Indeed, the problem of metaphysical deconstruction is primarily related to criticizing the language of metaphysics within the framework of the metaphysical deconstruction project.

However, in reality, it is not easy to criticize language: because when we criticize, we cannot go beyond the boundaries of this language. That is, in essence, we are in a kind of critical-hermeneutic circle: when criticizing metaphysical terms, philosophers themselves are forced to use them for criticism, thereby repeating all of metaphysics over and over again: "For... these simple concepts are not simple elements or atoms, but when included in a certain syntactic relation and a certain system, any particular connection leads to the entirety of metaphysics."

However, if the attempt to criticize the language of metaphysics fails and none of the philosophers takes responsibility for it, and if submission becomes inevitable, Derrida argues that any means of such submission is an alternative. According to him, the criterion for the quality and productivity of a particular discourse is "precisely its critical rigor, which is reflected in its connection with the history of metaphysics and inherited concepts." When Derrida reflects on the connection between speech and discursive inherited concepts, he

understands it as "an open and systematic statement of the issue related to the state of speech that has inherited the resources necessary to deconstruct this heritage."

Nietzsche and Heidegger criticized metaphysical concepts, striving to free themselves from them, and supplied the philosophical apparatus with neologisms. However, as we noted in paragraph 1 of the introduction to this study, the logic behind introducing new concepts was to abandon established meanings and encourage a revision of old terms. J. Derrida radicalizes this strategy and concludes that if a word escapes its intended meaning, then it is not necessary to invent new terms: the underlying idea is that they too can eventually "settle" and acquire a stable metaphysical meaning. Moreover, as indicated above, we cannot completely eliminate metaphysics from philosophical discourse merely by criticizing the language of metaphysics. Therefore, Derrida puts forward the following thesis: ..."There is no point in attempting to shake up metaphysics without using metaphysical concepts; we do not have a language (nor such syntax and vocabulary) that is alien to this history; we cannot advocate for such a destructive position that does not enter into the form, logic, and hidden relationships of the phenomenon we wish to object to."

In his work "Structure, Sign, and Play in the Discourse of the Human Sciences," Derrida identifies two methods of criticizing metaphysical concepts:

- a. engaging in systematic and rigorous questioning of the history of these concepts. Undoubtedly, this strategy is in many ways similar to M. Heidegger's hermeneutic strategy. As Derrida points out, this type of analysis belongs neither to the philological nor philosophical type, therefore it marks the first step towards going beyond the boundaries of metaphysics, as well as beyond the boundaries of philosophy itself. It is precisely "at the border of philosophy" that metaphysics can be critically analyzed (we will examine the marginal strategy in more detail below).
- b. Preserving all previous concepts as potentially useful tools while remaining within the framework of empirical research and demonstrating limitations everywhere. The uniqueness of this method is that it allows retaining metaphysical concepts, but with the understanding that they are under the sign of erasure, meaning they do not possess any absolute significance: "Henceforth, such tools are not assigned any truth value or strict meaning; they can be abandoned at times if other tools suddenly appear more convenient." Only through such relatively effective means, which do not become new absolute

tools, can the system of metaphysics be dismantled. This instrumentalism, applied in the field of philosophy, forms an anti-metaphysical methodology, where it is considered that "style can be separated from truth, means from style, and objective meanings aimed at revealing this style." Indeed, to prevent this method from falling into a set of tools, it is necessary to avoid absolutizing any method. Furthermore, this style indicates an existing field of anti-metaphysical activity characterized by the free play of meanings, and it is inappropriate to claim that this style is associated with any particular centralized meaning.

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